

Integrating Privacy Debt and VSE's Software Developments

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ABSTRACT

Abstract.

With the advent of regulations protecting users such as the General Data Protection Regulation, security and privacy concerns are playing a new role in small settings such as in very small entities. Their relevance is increasing, and privacy is being considered a Troy horse in software developments. In fact, privacy is a part of software architectural decisions, and they must be considered as a Technical Debt. The contributions of this paper are the following: a privacy debt definition with a principal and an interest, privacy related activities to be considered within the ISO/IEC 29110 basic profile, and the use of the net present value within this context. All these contributions help us to integrate Privacy Debt and VSE's software developments.

KEYWORDS: ISO/IEC 29110, technical debt, privacy, security

1 Introduction

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] in Europe, and other regulations such as the California Consumer Privacy Act of 2018 (CCPA) [2], and the Electronic Communication Privacy Act [3] in the United States of America are emphasizing and stressing the privacy concept which is tightly related to the security concept [4]. Software developments are increasing their complexity because most of them are not starting from scratch. In fact, new software systems are relying on pre-existing software components, libraries and so forth. Therefore, privacy can hardly be maintained in the resulting software systems. This situation implies that we need to analyse the impact of privacy and to determine whether Personally Identifiable Information (PII) [5] is present within the resulting software. There is not a silver bullet which automatically identifies and solves this issue. In fact, PII concept dates back in a U.S. Privacy Act 1974 for regulating personal information managed by government agencies [6].

Recent studies such as [7] and [8] analyse the privacy policy in mobile applications, and they highlight the relevance of privacy analysis within software applications. Privacy is not a simple requirement, and sometimes we need to go deeper on the analysis of different software. This means that static analysis is a starting point for identifying vulnerabilities and weaknesses related to privacy but we need check the behaviour of each tool [9]. Therefore, software developments must consider privacy and PII as main requirements, but it is not always managed and solved properly. Therefore, privacy and PII are becoming part of software architectural decisions, and they must be considered as a Technical Debt (TD) concept [10]. Privacy as a TD is a metaphor which pursues to manage privacy related "inoptimalities" from a static and dynamic points of view [11]. Recent studies on TD in software developments [12] are not considering privacy specifically.

There are studies related to how represent TD such as [13] where authors identify 10 types of TD related to the main activities in any software development process such as requirements, architecture, design, code, test and so on. From a privacy point of view, we need to consider different TDs along the software development phases because it is not a simple requirement nor single decision. There is a debate on which parameters should be considered during a privacy related analysis. Privacy can be ensured by applying different privacy preserving techniques [14]. Zengyang Li et al. [13] carried out a systematic mapping study on technical debt, and they used the ISO/IEC 25010 [15] standard as a reference for analysing the quality attributes (QA) compromised when TD is incurred. Privacy is not included directly within this set of QAs, and sometimes it is assumed to be considered as part of security concept.

Based on this context, we have identified the following research questions (RQs):

RQ1: *How can the privacy debt concept be defined?* This research question deals with the representation of a privacy debt, and its relationship with GDPR requirements.

RQ2: *How can the Privacy Debt be integrated within VSEs?* We add some activities to the ISO/IEC 29110 basic profile for managing privacy, and more precisely the privacy debt (PD) concept.

RQ3: *What is the financial impact on a PD?* We introduce a brief financial study which highlights the need of further research.

This paper is structured as follows. Firstly, authors provide a background on the main topics of this paper such as technical debt and privacy. Secondly, we introduce the PD concept. Thirdly, we identify privacy aspects within the ISO/IEC 29110 basic profile. Fourthly, authors analyse the net present value as financial concept within this context. Finally, we conclude this paper with a threat to validity section and some conclusions.

2 Background

2.1 TechDebt in software development

During these recent years, several researchers have paid attention to TD concepts, and several studies have been published on the topic. In this sense, and from a software development perspective, we tried to figure out what TD items can be expected along the development process. Despite the efforts devoted to figure out the variables for measuring TD elements such as principal and interest, there is scarce empirical evidence [16]. TD is a dual concept embracing subjective considerations as well as objective facts, especially for software developers. In fact, the self-admitted technical debt refers to situations in which software developers explicitly admit the introduction of technical debt in source code [17]. This is a normal practice in any software development because TD decisions are usually postponed to a later stage. . The reasons behind these decisions are not clear, but sometimes they are related to software developments themselves. In this sense, several challenges are identified by industry for the research community such as “code is checked by hand”, how to reduce debt, agile approaches, etc [18]. There is a common understanding that TD should be managed from the software development perspective [19], and being agnostic about the tools and trends such as DevOps [20]

In fact, once TD is properly introduced and explained, software managers can easily identify several types of TD during the development process[21]. However, it is not clear when and how these TDs influence the resulting software system. [22]. There are several studies characterizing current practices related to TD [23] or analysing potential TD when exchanging data s [24]. In

fact, software developers are usually solving their own TDs or even they are fixed by others [25]. which is an artisan style. The ideal situation would be to automatically identify and measure a TD [26]. The CISQ Quality Characteristic measures [27] provide a good base for measuring aspects such as Reliability, Performance Efficiency, Security and Maintainability. Basically these characteristics are based on the MITRE Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)[28], and on the ISO/IEC 25010 [15].

2.2 Privacy

Privacy is one of the most relevant concepts for consumers[29], and it is being considered by several regulations and standardisation bodies such as the International Organization for Standardization which defined a privacy framework [30]. In the United States of America, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) released the so called NIST Privacy Framework [31] which is used by enterprise as a guide for improving their privacy In addition, the Privacy by Design(PbD) [32] concept is becoming more relevant in software developments because organisations and individuals are more worried about how their privacy is used by the resulting software products. In this sense, we are surrounded by an uncountable set of devices gathering Personally Identifiable Information (PII) of customers. [32].

There are several Personally Identifiable Information (PII) definitions , and organisations such as NIST provide their own PII definitions [5]. In fact, these organisations are referring to the OMB Memorandum M-07-1616 [33] which defines PII as the information that can be used to distinguish or trace an individual's identity, either alone or when combined with other personal or identifying information that is linked or linkable to a specific individual [34]. One of the first definitions of PII dates back in a U.S. Privacy Act 1974 regulating the collection of personal information by government agencies [6]. But there are other references generalizing the PII concept where it includes any information that can be used to identify, contact, or locate an individual, and so forth [35].

In this sense, the protection of PII is envisaged as a hot topic and a cornerstone for any system involving personal data. For example, differential privacy has been used for protecting PII in Critical Infrastructure Data [36]. This issue is not only related to critical systems, but also to every organization collecting, processing, and transmitting customers' data or employees' data [37], because they are becoming attractive targets for cybercriminals.

2.3 Diagnosis of the situation

TD is a polyhedric concept overcoming objective and subjective concepts. Several researchers are providing useful insights and research works' results on this concept. From these results we can agree that software development approaches play a crucial role for identifying, maintaining and solving TDs. Therefore, there is a need to investigate on the role of software developments themselves.

As it has been highlighted, source code weaknesses and vulnerabilities are one of the most common TDs. They are easy to find and detect by using specific source code analyzers, and they are gathered in available databases.

Security and privacy are two intertwined concepts, and normally software developments are focused on strengthen security and to some extent on privacy. Security measures are well-known, and there are several tools and methods for improving security. However, privacy is a concept which is harder to guarantee because it involves different methods and tools that must

be considered along the software development process. In addition, if we merge privacy and technical debt, we need to clarify financial concepts

Therefore, we propose this research work where privacy debt is identified, and we include a financial aspect: Net Present Value

3 A privacy debt

This section is related to the research question: **RQ1: How can the privacy debt concept be defined?** This research question deals with the representation of a privacy debt, and its relationship with GDPR requirements.

If we analyse the GDPR, we realise that this regulation does not explicitly emphasise the privacy concept. In fact, it just references the Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications). In fact, there is no occurrences within the GDPR text (except the aforementioned directive). However, if we look for security term, we realise that there are 54 instances, and a specific section called “Security of personal data” (section 2).

According to Cambridge Dictionary, “privacy” means “someone’s right to keep their personal matters and relationships secret”. In fact, GDPR includes in section 2 a set of articles related “personal data breach” which are tightly related to the Cambridge Dictionary’s meaning of privacy. The distinction between security and privacy is out of the scope of this article, and authors are not going to discuss them. However, it is relevant to mention that GDPR ‘s article 32, 33 and 34 are related to personal data breach, and how to notify and communicate the breaches. According to this report [38] EUR272.5 million in fines have been imposed to companies related to GDPR’s infringements.

In the software development realm, specific measures must be defined and implemented for tackling privacy. It is therefore urgent to consider Privacy as a main requirement for any software development company, and to manage it along the software development process. As stated previously, most of software developments are not starting from scratch, and their developments are relying on pre-existing components made in house or imported from outside the organisation.

As privacy has an impact on the resulting software, we define **Privacy Debt (PD)** as the amount of efforts (resources) required for identifying, governing, controlling, communicating and protecting the software system along the software development lifecycle. This definition is aligned to the technical debt principal provided by Kruchten et al. [39] where the principal is proportional to the effort that a development team would expend to eliminate it. In fact, PD includes the efforts devoted to identifying, governing, controlling, communicating, and protecting (IGCCP) the privacy issues in a software system. Our approach uses the privacy debt’s metaphor where privacy has a principal and an interest based on the efforts devoted to activities mentioned earlier such as IGCCP. It is worth to mention that it is not a straightforward activity, and requires a deep analysis on the overall situation.

However, it is hard to measure these elements, because *There is a lack of empirical evidence on measuring Technical Debt principal and interest* [40]. A previous research work [41] we motivated the need and provided some hints on the concept. Here, we provide an approach aims to ease the PD principal calculation at each step of a development process.

- A PD is a short-term solution solving a privacy issue generating future interest payments.
- An interest is the extra cost to be paid.

We represent as a matrix (1) the efforts estimated for dealing with PD on each phase of a software development:

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{1,1} & \dots & a_{1,n} \\ \dots & a_{i,j} & \dots \\ a_{n,1} & \dots & a_{n,n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where i represents software development activities, j items represent NIST Privacy Framework core activities, and $a_{i,j}$ is the sum of the efforts devoted to fix and manage privacy:

$$\text{Privacy Debt principal} = \sum_{i,j=1}^{i,j=n} a_{i,j} \quad (2)$$

According to the previous definition, we consider an interest $ai_{i,j}$ as the extra cost to be paid because of the debt $a_{i,j}$. Similarly, we represent as a matrix (3) the extra cost on each phase of a software development:

$$\begin{bmatrix} ai_{1,1} & \dots & ai_{1,n} \\ \dots & ai_{i,j} & \dots \\ ai_{n,1} & \dots & ai_{n,n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Privacy Debt interest} = \sum_{i,j=1}^{i,j=n} ai_{i,j} \quad (4)$$

This matrix-based representation allows us to track and monitor the PD principal devoted on each phase. The *Privacy Debt principal* is incurred when refactoring or other remedial actions are used to fix and manage the Privacy from the software, whilst the *Privacy Debt interest* is paid in the additional cost due to the TD each time a privacy issue is solved.

This interest is not only related to this effort, but also with the different risks stemming from the mandatory regulations concerning privacy.

4 Integrating technical debt within VSE’s software developments

This section is related to the research question: RQ2: How can the PD be integrated within VSEs?

In the previous section, we have introduced the PD concept to be considered along the software development process. This PD approach can be used by any kind of company, but small companies are especially targeted because they are usually in rush dealing with developments pressure and other issues at the same time. As result, our focus is on improving their efficiency when they are dealing with privacy in software developments. As reference from a quality point of view we are using the ISO/IEC 29110 basic profile [42] because it represents the minimum set of quality assurance activities for small settings. In fact, this standard avoids overloaded or heavy weighted approaches which are not appropriate for this kind of companies. NIST Privacy framework and ISO/IEC 29100:2011 privacy framework define a set of activities which are tightly related, and each company should define their own approach. These frameworks are the basis of any approach dealing with privacy. The definition of a privacy related activities is not part of the contributions of this paper. Our aim is to create a generic approach, and we include the two most used privacy frameworks as example (Figure 1). In a previous work [41] we used the NIST privacy framework, but our approach is not to define a set of privacy related activities. Instead we want to highlight that for each software implementation activity we need to carry out a set of privacy related activities, and as result, we generate a PD.

The ISO/IEC 29110 [43] is used for representing the most common software implementation activities that a small company may carry out. It is relevant to note that the PD is spread over the different phases of a development project, and it should be managed along this lifecycle. This situation is graphically represented by Figure 1.

Figure 1: Privacy activities and ISO/IEC29110 software implementation activities producing PD

This ISO/IEC 29110 defines a basic profile[44] [42] with a set of activities from a management and software implementation point of views. Privacy has an impact on the project management activities, and we include the following activities:

- PM.1. Project Planning:
 - Systems/products/services processing PII are inventoried
 - Policies and Regulations are identified
 - Privacy Risk Management is identified
 - Contracts containing PII are identified
 - Roles and responsibilities related to privacy are established
 - Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control

- PM.2. Project Plan execution:
 - Systems/products/services are monitored
 - Policies and Regulations are monitored
 - Privacy Risk Management is monitored
 - Contracts are monitored
- PM.3. Project Assessment and control:
 - Evaluate privacy impact
- PM.4. Project Closure:
 - Checking Data processing ecosystem parties
 - Contracts and other obligations are checked

From a software implementation activities point of view, we add the following:

- **Software Implementation Initiation:** This initial phase must include an analysis of the data that it is going to be exchanged among systems. This data is analysed considering Data Security approach and the Protective Technology used. Concerning TD items related to privacy, we need to identify the datasets processed by the software system, the regulations, the stakeholders among others. As result, we obtain a set of Requirements PDs.
- **Software Requirements Analysis:** in addition to the traditional analysis of the requirements, the data is analysed considering the privacy requirements and the protective technology used within the project.
- **Software Architectural and Detailed design:** the selected protective technology is included within the resulting architecture. In addition, we need to add data security approaches, and we need to identify data processing policies, processes, and procedures.
- **Software Construction:** we use static source code analysis as well as dynamic approaches for identifying weaknesses. Code TD types are suggested to be included as PD.
- **Software integration and Test:** once the system is built, we need to evaluate whether the system compromises the privacy of the data.
- **Product Delivery:** this activity includes several checks in order to ensure we are delivering the appropriate product. Especially we analyse whether users' changes are consistent with privacy policies, processes, and procedures

5 A PD model from a financial perspective

This section is related to RQ3: *What is the financial impact of a PD?*

Once the PD concept and its relationship with software developments activities are defined, we need to proceed with the calculation of a PD. Until now, a PD has a principal and an interest, and basically these metrics are related to the efforts devoted (principal) and a interest. We are not going to define how an interest is calculated because it will depend on the resulting system. But there are other financial aspects to be calculated from a financial point of view [45] such as the Net Present Value [46]

Our PD concept approach is related to the efforts a company must devote to solve a privacy issue. This is a controversial topic as it is discussed in [47] where authors highlight that the sequence in which software development effort is estimated matters. Different methods can be used for estimating efforts [48], and it is a key aspect. However, our paper does not provide a new method for estimating efforts. We consider that stakeholders can identify these values.

Our approach analyzes the impact of financial concepts within the PD concept. In fact, we want to highlight the financial impact on small changes of the periods and the current cash flow. Seminal research works such as [13] identify elements such as principal or interest but it does not provide an order of magnitude for these elements, nor a hint on the periods and cash flow.

In our case we are considering that the amount of efforts is calculated with persons-month. Based on our experience, manageable issues can be solved by devoting efforts between 1 to 1000 persons-month. Obviously, this is an assumption that can be discussed later on, and it depends on the complexity of the issues. In the privacy context, we are considering the same order of magnitude for solving privacy issues.

In fact, the first element is to calculate the current value of future cash flows generated by the PD. This Net Present Value varies depending on future cash flows.

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^{i=n} \frac{R_t}{(1+i)^t} \quad (5)$$

where R_t refers to the net cash inflow-outflows during a period t , and i is the discount rate, and t refers to the number of time periods

We are considering the following options when dealing with privacy for an annual project.

Table 1. Cash flow simulation and t periods

Cash flow (PM)	t periods (months)
(-1, 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5 ,2)	(0, 1,2, 3,4,5)
(-5, 0, 5, 10, 15 ,20)	(0, 1,2, 3,4,5)
(0, 1, 1, 1, 1 ,1)	(0, 1,2, 3,4,5)

Net Present Value of an irregular cashflow (NPV) is complex to calculate but we need to simulate the cashflow and the dates when each cashflow occurs. This is represented in table 1 and in figure 2. We are considering that there are several milestones t periods where privacy is revisited and checked. Each period is related with 2 months per year. Concerning cash flow, we consider a positive cash flow.

Figure 2 Net Present Value calculation increasing the interest over the time: (a) for 3 short periods of time, (b) 6 periods of time

6 Threats to validity

Our research method requires an analysis and interpretation section following the guidelines provided by Wholin [49].

This paper is subjected to threats to construct validity, internal validity, and external validity.

6.1. Construct validity

Privacy is indirectly present in regulation such as GDPR because it does not explicitly refer to “privacy” along the regulation. However, security is being treated and considered on GDPR ‘s articles 32,33 and 34. In addition, software systems are relying on pre-existing software or components which are integrated for generating a resulting software system which is hardly to prove or to check. This fact makes privacy a relevant topic to be treated along software developments. Thus we have defined the PD concept based on Kruchten et al. [39] definition of TD. Our PD assumes a principal and an interest to be paid when dealing with privacy issues. This concept has been deliberately set aside in several software engineering communities because it is part of security field. It is worth to mention that the software engineering discipline must consider privacy as a cornerstone in any software development because, normally, any software processes data that can be related to PII. The concept of principal debt must consider the efforts would need to eliminate it. Obviously, there is a bias during this constructing process.

6.2. Internal validity

This paper is not an empirical study and there is a possible bias when defining or using this concept. From our experience, several experienced researchers believe they fully understand the privacy concept within the software developments, and they are reluctant to embrace the existing definitions and to transpose them into the software developments. In fact, we have been involved in several software developments where regulations must be satisfied with respect to the existing laws and norms. From the VSEs' perspective, we have included the most relevant aspects of the NIST privacy framework within the ISO/IEC 29110 basic profile. We have several experiences related to quality models [50], [51] and with the role of this standard. Concerning the financial analysis, we are assuming several assumptions which can be discussed. It is hard to figure out how to manage real PD even TD. We consider that principal and interest concepts are the building blocks, but we need to answer how other financial aspects such as the NPV are used within this PD context. For example, from a software development perspective how many periods should we consider? In our paper we are considering 6 t periods where a period is two months, and from a software development perspective we can set periods of two months for reassessing privacy within a software system. Another aspect which must be answered is the role of cash flow in software developments, and its relationship with a TD or PD.

6.3. External validity

External validity is related to what extend the outcomes of our research can be generalized. In this sense, we have used the ISO/IEC 29110 basic profile as a reference for software implementation activities and we calculated the PD. As stated on our approach, users need to perform privacy related activities based on the NIST Privacy Framework core functions or on the ISO/IEC 29100:2011 privacy framework

From a software development perspective, we are aware that not all software companies are following this ISO/IEC29110, but the approach for calculating the PD is independent from the software development used by the software development company. The defined matrix helps us to track the efforts assigned on fixing PD, and their interests. The privacy activities are related to well-known privacy related activities. However, we recognise more activities related to business risks, risk calculation, security risk may impact on the PD concept.

6.4. Conclusion validity

The conclusion validity is related to whether correct outcomes can be suggested from the experiment. In this sense, we cannot conclude anything because we are still carrying out the experiment, and we do not have statistics, and measurements are still immature.

7 Conclusions

We have defined the PD metaphor along the software developments as a special case of TD. Regulations such as GDPR are forcing companies to seriously consider security and privacy. Personal data breaches are hot topics and most of the times, leakages are performed because the resulting software systems were not considering all the situations, and the assumptions were not correct. The consistent management of privacy is not always trivial, and it used to be diluted among software development activities. Therefore, we have created this PD concept which is focused on privacy management.

At the beginning of this paper, we defined a set of research questions. In what follows, authors review them.

RQ1: *How can the privacy debt concept be defined?* A PD definition is provided, and it includes principal and the interest. It is worth to mention, that our approach helps us on tracing principal and interest per software development phase.

RQ2: *How can the Privacy Debt be integrated within VSEs?* We add the most relevant activities of the NIST privacy framework to the ISO/IEC 29110 basic profile. These activities are adapted to VSEs.

RQ3: *What is the financial impact on a PD?* We introduce the Net Present Value with the PD concept. It is not evident how to apply this financial aspect to this scenario and several assumptions should be considered.

As future work, we are working on other financial aspects that can be applied to this context. It is not obvious its application and sometimes we need to set some assumptions for adopting and using these financial concepts. Despite the efforts and the contributions described in this paper, there are several research lines to be strengthened such as how to calculate the interest from a quantitative point of view, or how to perform a privacy impact assessment within the software system.

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